

Procedures for improved quantitative energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy in transmission electron microscopes

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Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDXS) is a routine method for chemical analysis in electron beam instruments, i.e. scanning electron microscopes (SEM) or transmission electron microscopes (TEM). Its precision relates to self-consistency of individual as well as the reproducibility of consecutive measurements, both of which are often poor. For stoichiometric alloys like GaAs the Ga/As elemental ratio reported may be far off unity but will depend on which lines are chosen [1]. Most acquisition software packages decide automatically which X-ray lines they use for quantification (usually the hardest X-ray lines available, i.e. K lines preferred over L or M), however, choosing other lines manually can give significantly different results in case of both SEM-EDXS and (S)TEM-EDXS. While this may appear confusing, it allows for self-consistency checks that can improve reliable quantification in (S)TEM-EDXS of many semiconductors, by serving as internal self-calibration of absorption effects.

The number of X-rays detected from an element j in a sample of thickness t is given by the equation

$$I_j = N_A i \rho t c_j \sigma_j \omega_j f_j e_j \tau a_j / (A_j e)$$

where N_A is Avogadro's constant, i the probe current, ρ the sample density, c_j the weight fraction, σ_j the ionisation cross-section, ω_j the fluorescence yield, f_j the line partitioning fraction (for K, L, M lines), e_j the detection efficiency of line j , τ the measurement time, a_j the absorption correction factor, A_j the atomic weight of element j (in g/mol) and e the electron charge [2]. In SEM, contributions from all depth slices within the excitation volume are added, which increases the signal and allows full analytical modelling of X-ray generation and absorption, giving high sensitivity but low spatial resolution because the excitation volume is large [3]. In TEM, the specimen is a thin foil, the excitation volume is small so spatial resolution can reach sub-nm, but the signal is noisy and quantification relies on a correct absorption correction. There are only four options:

- i) thin film approximation after Cliff & Lorimer without absorption correction [4], where for any line pair i, j k -factors are defined as $k_{i,j} = (\sigma_j \omega_j f_j e_j A_i) / (\sigma_i \omega_i f_i e_i A_j)$,
- ii) measurement of the thickness and modeling of absorption assuming a certain density, then division of the k -factor for thin films by a built-in absorption correction factor $a \in (0, 1]$ (chosen by most quantification software codes) [1],
- iii) measurement of the probe current and use of the zeta-factor method [5],
- iv) quantification using the effective k^* factor method where $k_{ij}^* = k_{ij} a_j / a_i$ is the ratio of the thin film k -factor and the corresponding absorption correction factors and should be plotted not as function of real thickness but the K/L or L/M line ratio of one element [6]. For alloys where the concentration of the reference element is not constant when the one whose content is to be measured is varied (e.g. Ga in InGaN) one can get sets of calibration curves that necessitate an iterative solution, c.f. figures 7 & 8. Some applications to SiGe, InGaAs and InGaN are presented below.

Figure 1. Experimental Ge K/L ratios at 200kV measured for two different $\text{Si}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_x$ samples under various imaging conditions.

Figure 2. Consistent calculation of $k^*_{\text{GeK,SiK}}$ from over 50 X-ray spectra from both samples. All data points lie on one line.

Figure 3. Ge content from thin film k -factors (squares: Ge_K , triangles: Ge_L). Scatter is large.

Figure 4. Ge content from k^* -factors. Scatter is small. Dotted: nominal values.

Figure 5. Simulation of $k^*_{\text{InL,AsL}}$ for GaAs

Figure 6. Simulation of $k^*_{\text{InL,AsK}}$ for GaAs

Figure 7. Simulation of $k^*_{\text{InL,GaL}}$ for $\text{In}_x\text{Ga}_{1-x}\text{N}$

Figure 8. $k^*_{\text{InL,GaK}}$ for $\text{In}_x\text{Ga}_{1-x}\text{N}$

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